

The Recruitment, Retention, and Support for Black South Africans in Academia

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Even after thirty-two years of South Africa having equality and transformation policies, Black South Africans remain underrepresented as academics in universities. Previous studies conducted by other scholars have not focused on how Black South Africans are recruited and retained in universities. This present qualitative article closes the gap and looks at their recruitment, and the support is offered to Black South Africans in pursuing careers in higher academia. This includes how to retain them. The authors of this article found that in terms of recruitment as well as retention, trends are affected by elements such as temporary contracts, limited postgraduate pipeline, poor mentorship, inequitable access to research resources and career guidance for early-career academics. The findings further show that there are support programmes initiated by the government, such as National Research Foundation (NRF) funding, Nurturing Emerging Scholars (NESP), Black Academics Advancement Programme (BAAP), New Generation of Academics Programme (NGAP), and postdoctoral fellowships. These programmes provide opportunities for mentorship and career progression. Even though these programmes are available, the authors indicate the necessity for more awareness initiatives to be put in place to ensure that every Black South African is fully aware of these programmes.

Keywords: Recruitment, retention, black South African academics, higher education, transformation

Institutions of higher education remain affected by lack of diverse academics (Smith, 2024). This problem is prevalent in the entire higher education sector. It has led to several debates in the public and in the higher education sector as a whole. This is shown by scholars such as Deem, Case, and Nokkala (2022) acknowledged inequality in both students as well as the academic staff across universities. The authors further state that the terminology of inequality in higher education covers several wide ranges of topics, including racial discrimination. Theoretically, higher education is supposed to be characterised by diversity, innovation and social justice. However, scholars such as Dupree and Boykin (2021) discovered that in reality, higher education experiences racial inequalities that hinder the hiring and keeping of scholars from diverse racial backgrounds. This is why institutions of higher education continuously face challenges in recruiting and retaining black academics.

In response to the above challenge, many higher education systems have introduced strategies to attract and retain academics, particularly black academics, yet these strategies are often

unsuccessful (Kissoonduth, 2017). In South Africa, inequality is especially severe because of the apartheid era (Belluigi & Thondhlana, 2022), which deliberately prevented black South Africans from obtaining academic roles in higher education. This has led to inequality, lack of role models and low interest among Black South Africans interested in careers in academia. In the present moment, many institutions of higher education have not made a significant effort in hiring and keeping more Black South Africans in academia. Belluigi and Thondhlana (2020) said that because of the above, higher education is currently having more white academics instead of black people. Evidence indicates that white people in percentages are over half of the academic staff, as they represent 53.2% of the academic staff (Kissoonduth, 2017).

On the other hand, national demographics are 80.2% for 'blacks,' 8.4% for 'whites,' 8.8% for 'coloureds,' and 2.5% for 'Indian/Asians.' This has created an idea that academia is not for Black South Africans. As a result, it led to having fewer Black South Africans interested in pursuing careers in universities as academics. This problem persists despite South Africa being one of the nations which have pieces of legislations and policies such as the Employment Equity Act (EEA) and the Higher Education Act (HEA). Both of them foster diversity, inclusivity and transformation. The EEA fosters workplace diversity by removing discrimination, whereas the HEA focuses on inclusivity and transformation within academia. Although this is the case, black academics are still underrepresented in higher education (Kissoonduth, 2017). The consequence of this issue is that, if left unaddressed, this imbalance threatens the transformation agenda of higher education, exacerbating social and economic inequalities.

Although earlier research has explored the recruitment and retention of academic personnel, insufficient focus has been placed on black academics. Therefore, this remains an area of knowledge that the present article seeks to explore. It is for this purpose that the

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article exists to contribute to the body of knowledge by exploring factors influencing the recruitment and retention of black academics in South Africa. This article is motivated by the difficulty faced by establishments of higher education in attracting as well as keeping talented academics, especially black academics. This issue has persisted within the realm of higher education from the onset of democracy in South Africa in 1994, with very little published research conducted in this particular area (Kissoonduth, 2017).

It must be noted that this problem creates a problem of excessive turnover rates of black academics. This further leads to a case whereby most academic positions in higher education are continuously occupied by foreigners and white academics rather than black academics (Nkomo, 2018). It should be emphasized that this presents an issue for both the institutions of higher education and the nation, as black South Africans are not receiving equal opportunities in academic employment. As a result, it alters the perception of black South Africans, leading them to lose interest in pursuing academic careers and prompting existing black academics to contemplate leaving their roles. This article aims to develop tactics that can be used to recruit and retain more black South Africans in academia with intention of promoting diversity, inclusivity and transformation.

Review of Literature

Theoretical Framework

Human Capital Theory: The authors used the human capital theory in this article. As stated by Wuttaphan (2017) human capital is a vital component of each organisation. Nkgapele, Dlamkile, and Mofokeng (2025) compared to the heart of any organisation. Relating this to the article, human capital in the article refers to academics, whereas the organisations are universities, which serve as institutions of higher education. This theory is grounded on the idea that the education, skills and knowledge of the human capital are very important for each organisation (Oliveira & Holland, 2007). In the context of this article, academics serve as educated, skilled, and expert in their respective fields who play an important role in strengthening teaching, research and innovation in higher education. The above indicates that human capital is important, especially in higher education. This makes the acquisition and retention of human capital important as they help to create new knowledge, develop future professionals and create innovative ideas. The authors used this theory as it helps to explain the reasons why Black South Africans are still less represented in higher education. This is because the theory highlights the important elements, which are education, skills, and knowledge. The theory also helps to answer the question of how Black South African academics are supported to pursue careers in higher education as academics.

Defining Recruitment and Retention in the Context of Higher Education

The higher education sector has faced multiple difficulties with recruiting and retaining Black South Africans as part of the academic staff (Leontes, 2024). Before delving into the literature, the authors believe that it is important to define the key concepts of recruitment and retention. Aliyu (2021) defined recruitment as a procedure undertaken to bring new talent into an organisation, whereas scholars such as Aburub (2020) state that the process of attempting to keep this talent in the organisation after recruitment is referred to as

retention. These two terminologies play an important role in ensuring diversity, equity, and institutional excellence (Leontes, 2024). In the article, recruitment refers to the process universities undertake to draw in Black South African academics, while retention refers to keeping these academics for a long time in these universities.

South African Legislative Framework and Policies

The Constitution of the Republic of South Africa (1996)

Section 9 of the South African Constitution indicates support for equality, as it indicates that people of South Africa are equal. It further indicates there should not be any form of bias based on gender, race or language (Republic of South Africa, 1996). This implies that every individual in South Africa should be treated fairly and equally. This article speaks to universities as institutions of higher education, which must ensure that their hiring practices are fair and inclusive of Black South Africans. This also includes the retention practices, such as promotions, which must also be fair and inclusive. The above sentiments are stated by Section 195 (i) of the Constitution, which implies that public administration must portray diversity in the country (Republic of South Africa, 1996).

Employment Equity Act 55 of 1998

The Employment Equity Act (EEA) exists to foster transformation in the workplace. It is also in line with Section 9 of the Constitution, which indicates that no one should be discriminated against, despite their gender, race or language. In Section 15 of the EEA, there is a necessity for affirmative action which requires that there are measures put in place to ensure that black people, women and people living with disabilities are fairly represented (Republic of South Africa, 1998). In higher education, Mukong (2024) states that universities as employers are required to ensure that Black South African academics are recruited and retained to ensure a fair representation of women.

Higher Education Act 101 of 1997

The Higher Education Act exists to govern universities as institutions of higher education. Section 27 of this act prioritises transformation and raises the need for organisations to foster equity as well as redress the previous imbalance caused by the apartheid era (Republic of South Africa, 1997). In the context of this article, this indicates that all previously disadvantaged groups should be recruited by organisations, which are universities in this article (Mukong, 2024). This is to ensure that they are fairly represented.

National Development Plan (NDP) 2030

This policy entails the long-term goals that South Africa intends to attain by the year 2030. In chapter 9 of this policy, there is a call that the higher education sector must show the demographics of the country (Republic of South Africa, 2011). This article clearly shows the necessity to develop more Black South African academics to pursue careers in higher education. This includes retaining them as well to attain diversity across universities.

The Importance of Transformation in Higher Education

Transformation plays a huge role in higher education as it is not just a demographic representation but about equal access, participation

and opportunities. In other words, transformation is perceived as a mechanism for addressing injustices while fostering inclusivity (Adonis & Silinda, 2021). Historically, especially in the apartheid era, South Africa was affected by this era in the sense that black people were discriminated against, which has created multiple issues, such as inequalities. These issues have disadvantaged black people. In higher education, universities are still affected by the injustices and imbalances created by apartheid and barriers such as poor mentorship, limited career progression opportunities, and unconscious bias affecting Black academics (Leontes, 2024).

Attracting Black South African Academics in Higher Education

Earlier studies have shown that recruitment strategies in South

African universities often fail to attract sufficient numbers of academics (Mokoditso, 2011) especially black academics (Badat, 2010; Theron, Barkhuizen, & Du Plessis, 2014; Kisoonduth, 2017). One of the reasons is because some authors believe that most South Africans are less qualified to become academics, this is shown by the Public Servants Association (PSA) report, indicating that throughout South Africa, fewer than 3% of the population possess a bachelor's or honours degree, and merely 0.75% held a postgraduate qualification (Public Servants Association, 2016). Nkomo (2018) also highlights that the scarcity of Black South African academics results from the insufficient number of adequately qualified individuals with doctoral degrees in South Africa to fill academic positions. This claim is reinforced by the DHET (2019) report, which indicates the small number of South African students engaged in master's and doctoral studies, as illustrated in Table 1 below:

Table 1

South African Postgraduate Pipeline

Total Number of Students	Master's Degree Graduates	Doctoral Degree Graduates
Students Who Graduated	12 951	3 057
South African Students Graduated	10 186	1 732
Non-South Africans	2 765	1 287
South African Students Graduated (in percentages)	78.7%	56.7%
Non-South African Students Graduated (in percentages)	21.3%	43.3%

Observing the preceding statistics, it is evident that South Africa has achieved advancement with master's degree graduates, yet there is a limited number of South African doctoral degree graduates. The question arises whether these doctoral degrees are either inaccessible or difficult to obtain. Kotelana (2021) believes the reason for this is insufficient access to postgraduate funding and training, which will result in a shortage of highly skilled academics (professors) in South Africa. The danger to the above is that approximately 20% of these scholars are anticipated to retire within the coming decade, creating a gap in the higher education system. Another problem may be that some black academics are attracted to overseas universities that provide superior salaries and opportunities (Magoqwana, Maqabuka, & Tshoedi, 2019). This questions the support offered by the government through the Department of Higher Education and Training. It asks what support is given to South African academics to ensure that Black postgraduate students are trained to become the next generation of academics. The literature does not answer this, hence the existence of this article.

Keeping Black South African Academics in Higher Education

Earlier research has demonstrated that globally, the higher education system is facing difficulties in keeping academics. Pieters, Van Zyl, and Nel (2022) noted that the need for academics within higher education is anticipated to continue for many years, especially Black South African academics. The authors highlighted this because few young academics are entering higher education. They continue to face challenges in holding on to these essential personnel, who are expensive to train and difficult to replace. Gurmessa and Tefera (2019) stated that young academics leave higher education the most

compared to older academics. The author further alludes that young Black South African academics are needed to sustain and progress of the institution of higher education. Most of the previous scholars have noted that most of the turnover of Black South African academics is caused by multiple issues such as insufficient institutional support, heavy workloads, and a sense of isolation. The above notion has been evidenced by multiple scholars (McCarthy, Spencely, & Winstone, 2020; Pieters, Van Zyl, & Nel, 2022). This has led to employment dissatisfaction, which is believed to be the reason why many academics withdraw their participation from higher education. This shows the necessity for retention tactics, as the current tactics employed are failing to keep these academics. Such a challenge must be urgently addressed as it may create an impression that higher education is not meant for Black South Africans, and this may cause more turnover in the higher education sector. Based on the literature, it is clear that prior studies have been conducted, but their focus was not on retaining Black South African academics. This is an area which is not sufficiently addressed, which this current article intends to address.

Method

The authors of the article used a qualitative research approach and used secondary data, which has been made available by other researchers in the recruitment and retention of Black South African academics. To address the questions posed by this article, the authors collected all literature published by other researchers, together with a narrative literature review. This literature in mention was located using key concepts such as *Black South African academics, recruitment, retention, and higher education*. The data sources consulted by the authors were journal articles, credible online

materials, unpublished theses, policy documents, and news articles. This includes legislation and policies which were related to the article. To analyse the data gathered, a narrative literature review approach was used to reflect narratively and make arguments based on the current problems in the recruitment and retention of Black South African academics.

Results and Discussion

Recruiting Black South African Academics in South African Universities

A report on the Ministerial Task Team on the Recruitment, Retention and Progression of Black South African Academics revealed that some critical barriers and challenges impede the recruitment, retention, and progression of Black South African Academics, which block transformation in institutions of Higher learning in South Africa. In 2017, DHET (2019) stated that South Africa, 3,057 graduates for their PhD, of which South Africans were only 56.7%. This implies that most of 43.3% of these graduates were non-South Africans. Amongst the 3,057 that graduated, only 589 were Black South Africans, which equates to 19.29%, meaning that the remaining 80,71%. These percentages show that the postgraduate pipeline to produce PhD graduates is limited in South Africa. Scholars such as Kotelana (2021) are of the view that this is because many doctoral students struggle with funding opportunities, mentors, as well as capacity development programmes.

Because of the above, recruiting Black South Africans into universities remains difficult. Some scholars alluded that this is because most of the universities are not promoting transformation (Badat, 2010; Kisoonduth, 2017). The main factors remain practices such as lack of functional and reliable retention strategies, discrimination and university gatekeeping. The presence of the above hiring practices impedes the goal of transformation within higher education; the worst part is that there is a small number of Black South Africans in universities and those who would like to pursue academic careers. Nkomo (2018) indicated that in higher education, Black South African academics are offered temporary or fixed contracts, which affect their tenure within universities. It is important to note that such contracts hold a vital impact on their job and financial security. As a result, these academics are most likely to view most junior roles in higher education as unattractive (DHET, 2019). Such affects the main idea of transformation and inclusivity of Black South Africans as academic staff.

The idea is supported by Mkhize (2025) who has discovered that the failure of the universities to recruit Black South Africans is caused by factors such as university-related limitations, remuneration structures and intellectual abuse. Mkhize further stated that this has led to Black South Africans being mostly represented in junior roles than their counterparts. To add to the above, other factors such as migrations, where Black South African academics accept better employment opportunities in the industry or private sector. This is due to these industries and sectors' ability to offer good remuneration, benefits and career progression opportunities (Magoqwana, Maqabuka, & Tshoaedi, 2019). This notion is further advocated by a report produced by DHET (2019) clearly indicated that the lack of Black South Africans in South Africa is due to the institutions of higher education not being able to align their strategies with equality policies and legislation. This includes legislation such as the Constitution of the Republic of South

Africa (Section 9: Equality Clause) and the Employment Equity Act, which advocate that institutions of higher education should ensure that their hiring practices are aligned with these policies and legislation to attain inclusivity and diversity.

Retaining Black South African Academics in South African Universities

South African universities have been reported to be unable to retain academics for long periods. This is worse when it comes to Black South Africans. One can question if policies such as the Employment Equity Act and the Higher Education Act are actually operationalised in the higher education sector. Scholars have indicated that universities have a history of failing dismally to retain academic staff in higher education (Khumalo & Ndlovu, 2024; Ntshongwana, 2024). This is because of a lack of mentorship systems as well as the approaches in place. This is a clear indication that Black South Africans encounter issues such as constrained access to mentors who are senior academics who have sufficient experience. This issue alone can cause Black South Africans to lose interest in higher education due to insufficient mentorship (Kanyopa, Mokhele-Makgalwa, & Khanare, 2024). This creates a non-inclusive environment as well as a university culture. In turn, this translates to a lack of productivity, research, as well as doctoral completion rates, which in the future leads to more turnover from higher education.

Universities, according to a number of scholars are characterised by poor environments which do not foster inclusivity for Black South African academics, which adds to the existing issues with retention (Hlatshwayo, 2024a; Hlatshwayo, 2020; Zulu, 2021; DHET, 2019). In the view of Hlatshwayo (2020) Black South African academics are discriminated against, which has an impact on their sense of belonging and encourage them to depart from higher education sector as academics. DHET (2019) stated that Black South African academics often face issues such as lack of funding in terms of research as well as infrastructure, which serves as a barrier to their career progression. This affects their decision to remain in higher education. Other factors such as heavy workloads and administrative duties allocated to Black South African Academics at the early stages of their academic careers also affect their tenure in higher education. This is because such teaching and administrative duties affect their ability to produce new knowledge and complete their PhD.

Because of such, they are not able to progress professionally, which in turn translates to their departure from higher education (Hlatshwayo & Majozi, 2024). This speaks to the Human Capital Theory to advocate that universities should invest in the education, skills and knowledge of Black South African academics to ensure that they remain in higher education for a longer period. This is compounded by other financial issues, of which Musakuro and De Klerk (2021) believe are lower in higher education compared to what the industry offers, especially the private sector. This serves as the reason behind Black South Africans remaining in the private sector, government or going abroad. In other words, the majority of Black South African graduates are attracted to the industry over academic careers due to remuneration being higher than in higher education. These graduates also opt for the industry as it allows them sufficient time to spend with their family, friends and loved ones, which is difficult to have in higher education as an academic staff.

Factors that Influence the Representation of Black South African Academics in South African Universities

Studies have shown that there are broader issues that exist beyond the individual and departmental levels that influence the representation of Black South African Academics in South African universities (Hlatshwayo, 2020; Mkhize, 2025; Hlatshwayo & Majosi, 2024). Post the apartheid era, transformation has become an abused concept in South Africa. Universities in the past have committed to redress in their institutional strategies. However, there is a sense of transformation fatigue as institutions commit to redress on the article through strategic plans but fail to ensure that transformation is visible at the operational level. Hence, Black South African academics view transformation as mere theatrics (Leontes, 2024). This is exemplified by the commitment to transformation through the recruitment of Black South African academics, but in reality, it relies on international academics from Zimbabwe, Nigeria, Ghana, and East African countries (HSRC, 2023). This suggests that universities rely on international academics who already hold doctoral degrees and have established research and publication track records. They can produce research output in response to demands

for rankings and publication subsidies. Whereas Black South African academics are often faced with challenges that affect their research productivity, which does not work to the advantage of universities (Hlatshwayo, 2024). This is because universities want academics who produce research outputs, as universities rely on these outputs to generate income. The representation of Black South African academics is also due to the misalignment in coordination between bodies such as university councils, DHET, Universities South Africa (USAF), and the National Student Financial Aid Scheme (NSFAS) in transformation projects (DHET, 2025; DHET, 2023).

Support Offered to Black South Africans to Pursue Academic Careers

Given that several authors have noted that the recruitment and retention of black South African academics is characterized by conundrums and barriers to transformation (Hlatshwayo & Majosi, 2024; DHET, 2019; Heleta, 2017; Khunou, 2018; Maistry, 2025; Lockett, 2025). To overcome these conundrums, considerable progress is being made to alleviate these issues and enhance the situation. This is through the following initiatives of the government:

Figure 1

Support Mechanisms to Increase Black South African Participation in Academia

National Research Foundation (NRF) Postgraduate Scholarships	Nurturing Emerging Scholars Programme	New Generation of Academics Programme (NGAP)	NRF Black Academics Advancement Programme (BAAP)	Institutional and NRF funded Postdoctoral Fellowships
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Honours • Masters • Doctoral 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Honours • Masters 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Doctoral 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PhD Degree • PhD Track • Post-PhD Track 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Postdoctoral research

Note. Source: Author's own compilation

Firstly, the National Research Foundation (NRF) has funding instruments such as next-generation and emerging researchers. The next generation includes postgraduate funding opportunities for Honours, Master's, and PhD. There is a requirement of 65% on the previous degree (NRF, 2025). This is another attempt to recruit Black South Africans to pursue careers in academia. This is because one needs at least a master's degree to be a lecturer. However, A PhD is needed in the long run for one's career progression to senior academic posts such as senior lecturers, associate professors, and

full professors. This indicates that NRF is endorsing diversity in academia, which is also part of their mandate, which is "Transforming equity profiles of Postgraduate students and Researchers". The uptake for this postgraduate funding has been good. This is shown by the figure below, extracted from a presentation by the NRF Chief Executive Officer, Dr. Fulufhelo Nelwamondo, on 22 April 2025 to the Parliamentary Portfolio Committee on Science, Technology and Innovation:

Figure 2

Performance Information of NRF-funded Postgraduate Students

Outcome	Outcome Indicator	Five-Year Target	YTD Performance 2024/25
A Transformed (Internationally Competitive and Sustainable) Research Workforce	Profile of NRF-funded postgraduate students who have completed their studies	Black - 80%	Black - 86%

Note. Source: (NRF, 2025)

This Figure 2 shows the key performance information from the NRF Strategic Plan 2020 - 2025, demonstrating that a majority of funded black postgraduate students have completed their degrees. This achievement surpasses their initial five-year target of 80%, reaching 86%. NRF postgraduate funding has been complemented by other

initiatives such as the Nurturing Emerging Scholars (NESP) Programme. This programme was introduced to address the underrepresentation of Black South African and female academics by providing them with master's scholarships, internships, and placements in South African universities. These opportunities are

accompanied by mentorship and professional development opportunities. Currently, 63 opportunities have been made available for the 2025 academic year in 26 universities (DHET, 2024). Moreover, DHET has introduced opportunities, such as the Black Academics Advancement Programme (BAAP), through the NRF, to improve the postgraduate pipeline in South Africa and develop more black South African academics. This programme is in line with the equity and transformation objectives of the country.

BAAP supports only South African citizens employed at South African public universities as full-time academics (NRF, 2024). The equity target for this programme is to support South African citizens, being 90% African and 10% comprising Indian, Coloured, and persons with disabilities. The government of South Africa, through DHET, has invested massively in the recruitment and retention of Black South African Academics through initiatives such as the New Generation of Academics Programme (NGAP), which was established in 2015 by recruiting academics in line with equity needs. The most important features of the programme are that successful applicants are appointed into permanent posts firmly factored into long-term staffing plans right from the outset. Appointments are governed by contracts that clearly spell out the expectations, obligations, roles, and responsibilities of the employing university and of the newly appointed academic. Evidence shows that this programme has significantly transformed institutions of higher learning, as the DHET (2019) illustrated, with 373 NGAP positions allocated to black South African academics (DHET, 2016; UCT, 2024).

The support of the government does not end when South Africans complete PhDs. It further extends to the Postdoctoral Research Fellows (PRF). Kerr (2022) suggests that the objective of a PRF is to support the professional growth of recent PhD graduates as they prepare for a career in academia. It can, to a certain degree, be seen as a two-year academic 'apprenticeship' or internship. During this period, the Postdoctoral Fellow will engage in independent research and participate in the academic activities of the host School. Some of these fellows are funded by the NRF, while others receive funding from universities through their Research Office funds or council-controlled funds. These programmes are centred around mentorship as a pillar to improve the retention rate of black South African academics who have, in the past, faced challenges such as isolation and limited access to guidance and growth (NRF, 2025).

In addition, these programmes have conditions which promote flexibility and ensure that early-career academics have sufficient time for research. For instance, NGAP is a six-year programme that is divided into two stages, with the first stage being research-centred with a reduced workload and the second stage being a full workload period (DHET, 2016). This shows that there are clear developments to improve concerns such as heavy workloads, administrative duties relegated to early-career academics, which affect their retention and interest in being recruited to academic positions. Furthermore, universities have established clear institutional systems and structures. For example, the University of the Free State recruits early-career academics through three-year contracts, which are convertible to permanent on the basis that these academics obtain their doctoral degrees (Hlatshwayo, 2024b). These practices show that DHET together with universities are working hand in hand to ensure that South Africans are recruited and retained within higher education. This is aligned with the Human Capital Theory, which is in this case, is shown by the government's investment in developing

the education, skills and knowledge of South Africans to prepare them for academic careers.

Conclusion

The article concludes that universities still struggle in terms of recruiting and retaining Black South African academics. This is due to factors such as the pipeline of postgraduate studies to academic roles being little and fewer Master's and PhD completions by Black South Africans. The authors discovered that there are some challenges that make it difficult for Black South Africans to pursue academic roles such as unfair recruitment practices, poor mentorship, and racial discrimination. This is compounded by entering level roles in academia, where the remuneration is believed to be low, sometimes short-term contracts and low support, which makes them less attractive to Black South Africans. Because of this, the article found that the majority of Black South Africans opt for industry-related employment instead of academia. This demonstrates that recruiting Black South Africans encounters multiple issues and retaining them is also a problem. This is because most of them encounter non-inclusive environments, discrimination, heavy workloads, and limited access to research funding and resources. Such issues delay their progress, affect confidence and sense of belonging and eventually they depart from universities. Although the government is offering support such as NRF Postgraduate funding, the NESP, the NRF BAAP, the NGAP, and the NRF and institutional postdoctoral fellowships to recruit and retain Black South Africans. More work should be done in terms of raising awareness regarding these programmes.

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